

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE BULKHEAD CONSIDERING VARIABILITY DUE TO VARTM PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

A bulkhead for aircraft structure was fabricated with VaRTM process and its structural characteristics especially durability under the service condition were experimentally and numerically investigated. The bulkhead was designed according to FAR Part 25C. For molding of the skin panel, UD preform tapes were used. The preform tapes with narrow width were placed on a meridian of hemispherical shaped mold. This process created region with overlapped preforms at its longitudinal edges, which caused variability of thickness. Fatigue test was conducted by cyclically applying pressure loading. Displacement and strains were measured with gauges and FBG strain measurement system called OFDR. A finite element analysis with consideration of effect of the manufacturing process was conducted with a commercially available FEA software. Maximum displacement at the top of the hemisphere in the analysis well agreed with the experimental results. Strain distribution along the line corresponding to the FBG sensors was calculated. Due to thickness distribution affected by the manufacturing process, the strain distribution is undulating with the same trend observed in the experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Use of laminate composites is spreading for light-weight structure such as aircrafts because of its specific stiffness and strength. On the other hand, high-cost of the composite structure tends to lead limited application for expensive products. Low-cost manufacturing process such as VaRTM is one of the solution while large variability of structural characteristics due to such manufacturing process are not completely solved.

Numerical analysis such as FEA is indispensable tool for design of composite structure because of its complexity including anisotropy and its spatial distribution. However, effect of the variability due to the manufacturing process cannot be easily identified at the design phase because conventional use of FE software did not sufficiently consider the variability due to the manufacturing process. Draping simulation with FEA nowadays deal with this variability effectively.

This paper addresses how variability caused by VaRTM manufacturing process is processed in the framework of numerical analysis.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF THE COMPOSITE BULKHEAD

A bulkhead for aircraft structure was fabricated with VaRTM process to investigate its structural characteristics especially durability under the service condition [1]. The bulkhead was designed as shown in figure 1. Base differential pressure was set to 8.34 psi and limit load and ultimate load were determined to 11.8 and 17.7 psi respectively, complying to FAR Part 25C.

The skin panel was fabricated with UD preform tapes, Torayca T800-24K (Toray Industries Inc.). The preform tapes with width of 150 mm were placed on a meridian of hemispherical shaped mold at 150 mm interval on the top of the hemisphere. This process created region with overlapped preforms at its longitudinal edges. The amount of the overlap increases with the distance from the top of the hemisphere. This process was repeated for 4 times in angles of 0, +45, 90 and -45 degree. For heating the mold, 64 far infrared heaters were adopted to precisely control temperature. EP27 resin was used with 80 and 120 °C as first and second curing temperatures, respectively. Foamed cores (ROHACELL®) were inserted between preforms of the skin panel and stringers to avoid distortion of stringers due to pressure from vacuum bag as shown in figure 2.

Figure 1 Design of the bulkhead and location of measurement in the experiment

Figure 2 Fabricated integrated skin-stringer structure of the bulkhead

2.3 FATIGUE TESTS

An o-ring shaped aluminium structure was glued to the open flange of the bulkhead and the ring was tightly joined to a fixture with bolts and rubber seals to avoid air leakage as shown in figure 3. Air was cyclically inflated and released to the fixture to apply pressure loading of loading of 57.6 kPa to inside of the bulkhead. Loading profile is shown in figure 4. 1 cycle of loading approximately takes 100 seconds.

19 strain gauges were used to measure strain at location shown in Figure 1(a). The first letter “S” and “T” mean uni-directional and rosette strain gauges, respectively. Displacement at the top of the hemisphere was also measured with an extensometer.

Strain distribution along lines shown as “FBG” in the figure is measured with a FBG strain measurement system called OFDR. With this measurement system, in-situ measurement of strain distribution along a FBG sensor with length more than 1000 mm and resolution less than 1 mm can be conducted [2].

Figure 3 Setup of experimental fixtures

Figure 4 Time history of the pressure loading applied in the experiment

2.4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Strain distributions measured from 3 FBG sensors are shown in figures 5 to 7. Its time history shows that the strain linearly increased with increase of pressure load. Distribution of strain did not change after several cycles of the loading. It is considered that significant failure in the structure did not occur. Because FBG1 is attached to top of a stringer, the distribution is smooth compared to other FBGs. FBG2 and FBG3 are attached to skin paned, which is expected to have variable thickness due to the manufacturing process, have large scatters. The scatter in measurement of FBG3 is especially large because of small effect of reinforcement of stringers which is placed far from the FBG.

Figure 5 Measurement from FBG1

(a) corresponding location (b) time history of strain distribution (c) Strain distribution

Figure 6 Measurement from FBG2

(a) corresponding location (b) time history of strain distribution (c) Strain distribution

Figure 7 Measurement from FBG3

(a) corresponding location (b) time history of strain distribution (c) Strain distribution

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

3.1 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A finite element model of the bulkhead was created with a commercial pre and post-processing software, MSC Patran as shown in Figure 8. Aforementioned manufacturing process was modelled with Patran Laminate Modeler. Static structural analysis was conducted with a finite element code, MSC Nastran. Composite parts were modelled with composite shell elements in which integration points were individually placed in thickness direction for each layer of the composite. The composite parts were treated as integrated structure by using a capability of glued contact in the finite element solver. The o-ring shaped fixture, which was modelled with ordinary shell elements, was connected to composite parts with bush elements representing bolts. Bottom surface of the fixture was constrained in all direction and pressure loading of 57.6 kPa was applied on the back side of the skin panel.

Figure 8 Finite element model and boundary conditions

3.2 DRAPING AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Draping analysis with finite element model enables calculation of fiber orientation of laminate composites considering its manufacturing process. From element sets composing net-shape of the curved structure, flat state of the prepreg or preform are calculated. Straight fiber in the flat state are mapped to the curved structure based on the flat state. The calculated fiber orientations are transformed to local coordinate systems of the elements and output to FEM data. The draping analysis follows general procedure below.

- Material definition
User defines parameters of materials including thickness of prepreg used in manufacturing process and maximum angle of skew of warp and weft in a case of woven laminates.
- Lamina definition
The user defines element sets correspond to region of a specific prepreg in the structure. Flat state of the prepreg is calculated based on origin and direction of draping input from the user.
- Laminate definition
The user defines stacking sequence of laminates consists of laminae defined above. This step defines ply drop off without any additional input.
- Generation of input deck of FEA
The program calculates local coordinates system of all elements correspond to the calculated fiber orientations.

After the draping analysis, linear-elastic finite element analysis was conducted to simulate the structural behaviour of the bulkhead. All layers of laminate shell elements have local coordinate systems corresponding to the fiber orientation calculated in the draping analysis.

Figure 9 (a) Calculation of flat state of the pre-form tape (b) Mapping of fiber orientation to curved surface based on the flat state

Figure 10 procedure of draping analysis for 10 different placements of the pre-form tapes

3.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a result of the draping analysis, thickness distribution affected by the manufacturing process was obtained as shown in figure 11. Overlapped portion of the pre-form tapes are thickened, which causes complex thickness distribution which is not expected in the design.

Displacement, strain and stress distributions were extracted from the result of the FEA. Maximum displacement at the top of the hemisphere in the analysis was 1.3 mm, which is within a range from 1.1 to 1.4 mm in the experimental results. Contour bands of maximum principal stress and strain distributions are shown in figure 12 and 13. Variation due to the thickness distribution can be clearly observed. Calculated strain distribution along the line corresponding to the FBG sensors are shown in figure 14 to 16. Strain distribution from FBG sensors were processed with noise reduction filter to compare the FEM results. Because FBG1 is attached to top of a stringer, smooth distribution of strain was observed. For FBG2 and FBG3 which are attached to skin panel, undulated distribution affected by the manufacturing process are observed from both of experimental and FEA results.

Figure 11 Thickness distribution obtained from the draping analysis

Figure 12 Distribution of maximum principal stress in FEA

Figure 13 Distribution of maximum principal strain in FEA

Figure 14 Comparison of FEA and measurement from FBG1

Figure 15 Comparison of FEA and measurement from FBG2

Figure 16 Comparison of FEA and measurement from FBG3

4 CONCLUSION

A pressure bulkhead made with laminate composites was manufactured by VaRTM process. The structure has large variability of thickness due to manufacturing process where curved structure is built by combination of pre-form tapes with small width. Structural characteristics of the bulkhead were investigated by fatigue tests with a measurement system called FBG-OFDR. Measured distribution of strain shows significant oscillation affected by the variability of thickness.

Numerical analyses considering the manufacturing process were conducted with commercially available FEM software. Draping analysis shows that the manufacturing process causes thickness distribution due to overlapped portion of the pre-form tapes. Strain distribution calculated by structural FEA has significant undulation caused by the thickness distribution, which corresponds to the oscillation in the measurement.

Designer of composite structures is able to know how the manufacturing process affects structural characteristics by combination of draping and finite element analyses.

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